

ARIA Field Sets over API

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ARIA has several instances where it is possible to enter data using custom fields sets. For example, the proposal and visit fields are configurable based on the access route. Review and technical review, visit feedback, etc.

Selected fields are made available over several different APIs, but since they are configurable, the exact usage of these field sets vary. However, the basic concept is as follows:

- 1) Use a query to extract the expected fields for the context that you are submitting responses to (e.g. a proposal entry)
 - a. For example, you may also want to add extra fields to a proposal based on visit and services selected.
- 2) Render these fields in order and collect user input
 - a. Each field has several descriptive elements, including the type of field being rendered and how it should be configured (e.g. max characters, min / max values, etc)
 - b. Each field has a REF, this is used to address the field and associate it with data on submission
- 3) Submit the field data back as part of whatever submission mutation is appropriate (e.g. updateProposal, or saveTechnicalReview).
 - a. The exact mutation and parameter changes based on context
 - b. However, the data is always submitted as an array of objects, each object contains a "ref" field and a "value" field.

Origins and Mutations

Here is a non-exclusive list of all the form fields, the queries they're from, and the mutation that is used to submit the data.

Entity	Field Origin Query(s)	Update Mutation
Proposal	access_fieldsItems	updateProposal
Technical Review	access_technical_review_fieldsItems	saveTechnicalEvaluation
Visit feedback (user)	access_user_feedback_fieldsItems	submitUserFeedback
Visit feedback (facility)	access_facility_feedback_fieldsItems	submitFacilityFeedback

Anatomy of a field

There are a number of field options that are common across all field types, these are listed below. There is also always an associative field which links the query to the *thing* in ARIA. So, for example, for the Access_fieldsType query, which returns the proposal fields associated with a given access route, this would be the field access_id.

Important common fields are listed below:

Field	Type	Comment
ref	string	A generated or manually set “friendly” reference for referring to this field during uploads.
title	string	The field label
type	String	CUSTOM ¹ , TEXT_SHORT, TEXT_LONG, TEXT_NUMERIC, TEXT_URI, TEXT_DATETIME, TEXT_TAGS, WYSIWYG, TEXT_EMAIL, BOOL_SIMPLE, BOOL_EXT, BOOL_VERIFY, BOOL_FILE, SELECT_SIMPLE, SELECT_SCORE, SELECT_OTHER, TOTALLER, COLOR, PUBLICATIONS, FILE ² , RECAPTCHA, HEADER, DISPLAY_TEXT, CAREER_STAGE, PROPOSAL_LINK, APPLICATION_LINK
required	int	Boolean 1 or 0
options	JSON Object	Contains JSON settings for the control. These are field specific, but might include the maximum number of characters, help text, ranges for scores, whether a control accepts multiple values, etc
order	Int	Display order of the fields

¹ CUSTOM should be better thought of as a complex type, and is used for anything “complex” such as the EOSC work package details control. Details will be in the OPTIONS block.

² File uploads are necessarily handled in a special way, see details in the “Handling file uploads” section

Submitting fields

As mentioned previously, the field set data should be submitted back as part of the relevant mutation.

In each instance, this data field will be an array of the following objects:

Field	Type	Comment
ref	string	The reference for this field
value	json	Json encoded value for this field

Handling file uploads

File handling necessarily requires you to upload the file to a REST file upload endpoint first by performing a multipart form upload to one of the following endpoints:

Environment	URL
Live	https://instruct-eric.org/api/files/file
Beta	https://beta.structuralbiology.eu/api/files/file
Test (internal for Instruct)	https://test.instruct-eric.eu/api/files/file

You must authenticate this query using the same Bearer token as you authenticate any other API call.

You will be returned, on success, a blob of JSON, e.g.

```
{
  "orig": "My CV.pdf",
  "name": "k .. ab.pdf",
  "size": 468992,
  "type": "application/pdf",
  "debug_size": "chunk: 468992, file: 468992",
  "url": "https://instruct-eric.eu/upload/k..ab.pdf",
  "deleteUrl": "ajax/action.data.upload?file=k..ab.pdf",
  "deleteType": "DELETE"
}
```

It is this JSON that you should upload when submitting the content for this field.

Version History

Version	Description
0.1	Initial draft